

THE INFLUENCE OF STUDENTS' LEARNING DISCIPLINE ON LEARNING ACHIEVEMENT IN SOCIAL STUDIES SUBJECT AMONG GRADE VII STUDENTS AT SMP NEGERI 10 PEMATANGSIANTAR

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Abstract

This study aims to examine the effect of learning discipline on students' academic achievement. The research instruments used were a learning discipline questionnaire and an academic achievement questionnaire, both of which had been tested for validity and reliability with satisfactory results. The normality test using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov method indicated that the data were normally distributed, with a significance value of 0.200 greater than 0.05. Simple linear regression analysis produced the equation $Y = 60.135 + 0.258X$, which demonstrates a positive relationship between learning discipline and academic achievement. The regression significance test showed that the t-value of 11.417 was greater than the t-table value of 1.67203 at a 5% significance level, and the significance value of 0.002 was less than 0.05, indicating that learning discipline has a positive and significant effect on academic achievement. The coefficient of determination (R Square) was 0.150, meaning that learning discipline contributed 15% to academic achievement, while the remaining 85% was influenced by other factors outside the scope of this study.

Keywords: *Learning discipline, Academic achievement, Simple linear regression.*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role in shaping a generation that is intelligent, virtuous, and capable of facing global challenges. Article 3 of the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System states that the function of national education is to develop and shape the character and civilization of a dignified nation in order to enlighten the nation's life, in order to develop the potential of students to become people who believe in and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. The challenges of education in Indonesia are increasingly complex. One significant challenge is ensuring optimal student achievement. Learning achievement is the achievement students attain after participating in the learning process and encompasses cognitive, skill, and attitudinal aspects. Student achievement is the result of the learning process, encompassing knowledge, skills, and attitudes. One factor that significantly influences learning achievement is learning discipline. Students who demonstrate high levels of discipline, such as attending school on time, completing assignments regularly, and paying attention to teacher explanations, tend to achieve better learning outcomes. Conversely, a lack of discipline can lead to students being careless and unfocused, resulting in declining learning achievement.

Field observations indicate that student discipline remains low. Based on my observations, at the UPTD of SMP Negeri 10 Pematang Siantar, many seventh-grade students still do not comply with learning regulations, such as not completing homework on time, arriving late to class, skipping class, paying little attention when the teacher explains the material, and rarely preparing themselves before the lesson begins. This has an impact on low student achievement, especially in Social Studies (IPS). In the context of Social Studies (IPS) learning, academic achievement plays a crucial role because this subject not only equips students with knowledge of the social environment but also develops critical thinking skills and informed decision-making in social life. Therefore, a thorough understanding of the factors influencing academic achievement in IPS is crucial for improving the quality of learning in schools.

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Learning achievement can be measured and expressed in the form of grades listed on report cards. These grades serve as the primary benchmark for determining a student's level of success in understanding and mastering the material taught in class. If a student's grade is above the average (KKTP), then the student is considered to have successfully achieved the predetermined learning objectives. Conversely, if a student's grade is below the average KKTP, this indicates that the learning objectives have not been fully achieved. In line with the explanation above, the results of observations conducted by researchers at the school indicate that in grade VII, there are still a large number of students who have scores below the KKTP. Judging from the data obtained by the UAS scores of grade VII students in social studies at SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar, it shows that most students still have not achieved the KKTP score.

Table 1.1 Details of the Final Exam Scores for Class VII Students of SMP Negeri 10 Pematang Siantar for the 2024/2025 Academic Year

Class	Number of Students	Family Card (KKTP)	Final Exam Score			
			A (90-100)	B (81-90)	C (71-80)	D (<70)
VII-1	34	75	-	9 Students	25 Students	-
VII-2	34	75	-	7 Students	27 Students	-
VII-3	35	75	-	10 Students	22 Students	3 Students
VII-4	34	75	-	12 Students	19 Students	3 Students
VII-5	33	75	2 Students	6 Students	25 Students	-
VII-6	33	75	-	5 Students	28 Students	-
VII-7	33	75	-	8 Students	23 Students	2 Students
Total	236		2 Students	57 Students	169 Students	8 Students

Based on the final exam results of grade VII students at the UPTD of SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar, out of a total of 236 students, the majority, or around 71.61%, obtained grades in category C (71–80). This indicates that the majority of students were only able to meet the minimum completion standards set out in the Learning Objectives Achievement Criteria (KKTP). Meanwhile, 24.15% of students obtained grades in category B (81–90), which reflects a fairly good mastery of the material, although not yet optimal. Only 0.85% of students managed to achieve grades in category A (90–100), indicating that achieving excellent grades is still very limited. On the other hand, there were 3.39% of students who obtained grades below 70 or fell into category D, which means they have not achieved learning completion. Overall, 96.61% of students have achieved grades according to KKTP. However, the dominance of students in category C indicates the need to improve material understanding and learning motivation so that more students can achieve higher grade categories.

The data also shows that only 59 students, or about 25% of the total, were in the good and very good (A and B) grades. This achievement is still far from the expectations of the seventh-grade social studies teachers at the UPTD of SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar who targeted more students to achieve A and B grades. The high number of students in category C and the continued presence of students in category D reflects obstacles in the social studies learning process, both in terms of material understanding and student learning discipline. This indicates that the learning achievement of seventh-grade students in social studies is still relatively low and has not fully met the expected learning targets. Thus, it can be concluded that although the level of learning completeness has been met quantitatively by the majority of students, qualitatively the social studies learning achievement of seventh-grade students at the UPTD of SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar is still relatively low. A more student-centered learning improvement strategy, strengthening learning discipline, and the active role of teachers and parents are needed to encourage students to achieve higher and more meaningful learning outcomes.

METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach with descriptive methods and simple linear regression analysis. The study aims to determine the effect of learning discipline on the social studies learning achievement of seventh-grade students of UPTD SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar in the 2024/2025 academic year. The location of the study was carried out at UPTD SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar with a population of all seventh-grade students totaling 236 students. The research sample was taken at 25% of the population, resulting in 59 students using the proportional stratified random sampling technique.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Simple Linear Regression Test

The results of the simple linear regression test can be seen in the following table:

Table 1 Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	60.135	6.352		9.466	.000
	Disiplin	.258	.079	.398	3.279	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Y2

(Sumber: SPSS versi 26,2025)

From the results of the regression test above, a simple linear regression equation can be obtained as follows: $Y = 60.135 + 0.258x$ and the coefficient value is positive (+) and the significant value (sig) is $0.002 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the influence of student learning discipline has a positive effect on student learning achievement.

t-test (Partial)

The partial test or t-test is a partial regression coefficient test to determine the partial significance of each dependent variable on the dependent variable. The t-test is used to test whether there is a relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 2 t-Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	112,046	9,814		11,417	.000
	Discipline	-.387	.122	-.388	-3,177	.002

a. Dependent Variable: Achievement

From table 2 it can be seen that the test results for the student discipline variable (X1) show a t-count value of 11.417 and a t-table value of 1.67203, so it can be concluded that $t\text{-count} > t\text{-table}$ ($11.417 > 1.67203$) so that H_a is accepted. Thus, there is a positive and significant influence between student discipline on student learning achievement in the subject of Social Studies class VII UPTD SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar

Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination test was used to measure the extent to which learning discipline as a learning achievement influences the social studies learning achievement of grade VII students at SMP NEGERI 10 PEMATANG SIANTAR. To measure the percentage value, the coefficient of determination test was conducted as follows:

Table 3 Results of the Determination Coefficient Test

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Standard Error of the Estimate
1	.388 ^a	.150	.136	5,048

a. Predictors: (Constant), Discipline

Based on the table above, the coefficient of determination is 0.150, so it can be concluded that the variable of learning discipline (X1) has a contribution of influence on the variable of learning achievement (Y) in students of SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar by 15%. While the remaining 85% is influenced by other factors that were not researched.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the data analysis obtained, the learning discipline questionnaire instrument has undergone validity and reliability tests with adequate results. Of the 25 statement items compiled, 20 items were declared valid because they had a calculated r value greater than r table at a significance level of 5%, while the other 5 items were invalid and therefore were not used in subsequent analyses. The reliability test showed that the learning discipline instrument obtained a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.775, which is above the minimum limit of 0.60. This proves that the instrument used is reliable and suitable for use in research. The learning achievement questionnaire instrument has also been tested for its validity and reliability. Of the 25 statement items compiled, 20 items were declared valid and 5 items were declared invalid. The reliability test produced a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.772, which is also above the minimum limit of 0.60. Thus, the learning achievement instrument is declared reliable and can be used in research.

Data normality testing using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed that both variables were normally distributed. The significance value obtained was 0.200, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that the research data met the assumption of normality. This result indicates that the data are suitable for further analysis using simple linear regression. Based on the results of a simple linear regression analysis, the regression equation $Y = 60.135 + 0.258X$ was obtained. This equation shows that every one unit increase in the learning discipline variable (X) will be followed by an increase in learning achievement (Y) of 0.258. The regression coefficient is positive, which means there is a unidirectional relationship between learning discipline and learning achievement, meaning that the higher the level of student learning discipline, the higher the learning achievement achieved. The regression significance test showed a t -value of 11.417, which is greater than the t -table of 1.67203 at a 5% significance level. The significance value of 0.002 is also smaller than 0.05, so it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between learning discipline and learning achievement. Thus, the hypothesis stating that there is a positive and significant influence of learning discipline on student learning achievement can be accepted.

Furthermore, the results of the determination coefficient analysis show that the R Square value is 0.150. This means that learning discipline contributes 15% to the variation in student learning achievement, while the remaining 85% is influenced by other factors outside the variables studied, such as motivation, learning interest, environmental conditions, and family and teacher support. This finding indicates that although the influence of learning discipline on learning achievement is significant, its contribution is still limited so that other factors also need to be considered in efforts to improve student learning achievement. Thus, learning discipline is proven to provide a positive and significant contribution to student learning achievement, although there are still other factors that influence students' overall academic achievement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that learning discipline has a positive and significant influence on the social studies learning achievement of grade VII students at UPTD SMP Negeri 10 Pematangsiantar. The results of simple linear regression analysis show the equation $Y = 60.135 + 0.258X$, with a significance value of $0.002 < 0.05$. This proves that the higher the student's learning discipline, the higher the learning achievement achieved. The t -test shows that t count of 11.417 is greater than t table of 1.67203, so the research hypothesis is accepted. In addition, the coefficient of determination (R Square) of 0.150 indicates that learning discipline contributes 15% to learning achievement, while the remaining 85% is influenced by other factors not studied.

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